

Exploring A Simple Integer Periodic Sequence With Connections to Modular Forms and Representation Theory

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Abstract

We introduce a simple period 8 integer sequence that exhibit symmetry, periodicity, and oscillatory behavior, revealing connections to modular forms, representation theory, harmonic analysis, and number theory. The sequence is the simplest of a family of periodic integer sequences and corresponding trigonometric formulations involving exponential and cosine functions. By focusing on a specific sequence of this family, we briefly explore some insights into its structural characteristics that connects to well-established mathematical theories. This work serves as an introduction for further exploration into the underlying principles governing this family of sequences.

1. Introduction

Periodic sequences play a fundamental role in various areas of mathematics, including number theory, combinatorics, and mathematical physics. They often encapsulate deep structural properties and can reveal surprising connections between different mathematical domains. In this paper, we present a periodic integer sequence and its corresponding trigonometric formula, which serves as the simplest representative of a broader family of sequences we have uncovered that both individually and collectively, these sequences reveal deep mathematical connections.

Our goal is to understand the mathematical properties of this sequence and its concrete connections to modular forms, representation theory, harmonic analysis, and number theory. By providing explanations of what we observe we aim to stimulate further research and collaboration in uncovering the underlying principles of this sequence family.

2. The Periodic Sequence

2.1 Description of the Sequence

Consider the following periodic sequence with a period $N=8$:

$$\{1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$$

With a period:

$$a(n) = 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3 \text{ for } n \geq 0$$

$$a(0) = 1, a(1) = 3, a(2) = 2, a(3) = 1, a(4) = 2, a(5) = 1, a(6) = 2, a(7) = 3$$

The sequence repeats indefinitely, with terms defined as:

$$a(n) = a(n - 8) \text{ for } n \geq 8$$

This sequence exhibits symmetry and an oscillatory pattern among the integers 1, 2, and 3, arranged in a specific order that reflects underlying mathematical structures.

2.2 Family of Sequences

This sequence is the simplest member of a broader family of periodic sequences, each defined by similar trigonometric formulations and sharing common properties such as symmetry, periodicity, and harmonic components. These sequences vary in period length and complexity but are united by their structural characteristics and mathematical significance.

2.3 Formulas

2.3.1 Modular Arithmetic Definition

The sequence can be described using modular arithmetic for $n \geq 0$:

- $a(n) = 1$ if $n \bmod 8 \equiv 0, 3, \text{ or } 5$;
- $a(n) = 2$ if $n \bmod 8 \equiv 2, 4, \text{ or } 6$;
- $a(n) = 3$ if $n \bmod 8 \equiv 1 \text{ or } 7$.

This explicit definition provides a straightforward method to compute the sequence terms based on the residue of n modulo 8.

2.3.2 Generating Function

$$G(x) = \frac{(1 + 3 * x + 2 * x^2 + x^3 + 2 * x^4 + x^5 + 2 * x^6 + 3 * x^7)}{(1 - x^8)}$$

This generating function encapsulates the periodicity of the sequence through the denominator $1 - x^8$ and the specific pattern is encoded in the polynomial coefficients in the numerator, reflecting the oscillatory behavior of the sequence.

2.3.3 Trigonometric Formulation

The sequence can also be expressed using a trigonometric formula:

$$a(n) = \frac{1}{8} (15 - e^{i\pi n} [c_0 \cos \frac{0\pi n}{4} + c_1 \cos \frac{1\pi n}{4} + c_2 \cos \frac{2\pi n}{4} + c_3 \cos \frac{3\pi n}{4}])$$

Where:

$$c_0 = 1$$

$$c_1 = (2 + 4\sqrt{2})$$

$$c_2 = 2$$

$$c_3 = (2 - 4\sqrt{2})$$

This formulation represents the sequence as a sum of cosine functions with specific frequencies and amplitudes, reflecting its harmonic components. The exact coefficients and frequencies indicate precise harmonic relationships inherent in the sequence's structure.

3. Mathematical Connections

This section concisely shows how the sequence connects with various mathematical domains.

3.1 Connection to Harmonic Analysis

3.1.1 Fourier Series and Periodic Functions

Any periodic function with period T can be expressed as a Fourier series:

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} c_k e^{2\pi i k t / T}$$

where the coefficients c_k are given by:

$$c_k = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(t) e^{-2\pi i k t / T} dt$$

For discrete sequences, the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) provides an analogous decomposition.

3.1.2 Application to the Sequence

Our sequence $a(n)$ can be viewed as samples of a periodic function defined at integer points. The trigonometric formula represents $a(n)$ as a finite sum of cosine functions, which corresponds to the inverse DFT of its frequency components. Specifically, the sequence can be reconstructed exactly from its harmonic components, indicating that the trigonometric formulation is precise and not merely an approximation.

This exact representation aligns with harmonic analysis principles, where functions (or sequences) are decomposed into sums of orthogonal basis functions—in this case, cosine functions with specific frequencies and amplitudes.

3.1.3 Interpretation of Harmonic Components

The frequencies $\frac{\pi n}{4}$, $\frac{\pi n}{2}$, and $\frac{3\pi n}{4}$ correspond to fundamental frequencies of the sequence's period. The coefficients c_0 , c_1 , c_2 , and c_3 determine the contribution of each harmonic to the overall sequence.

This harmonic decomposition reveals the underlying oscillatory behavior and symmetry of the sequence. It demonstrates that the sequence is not just periodic but also possesses a rich harmonic structure that can be analyzed and understood through the lens of harmonic analysis.

3.2 Connection to Representation Theory

3.2.1 Representation Theory Basics

Representation theory studies how groups act on vector spaces via linear transformations. Characters are functions that assign to each group element the trace of its corresponding linear transformation in a representation.

3.2.2 Group Representations and the sequence

The cyclic group C_8 of order 8 has irreducible representations corresponding to the 8th roots of unity. The characters of these representations are given by $\chi_r(n) = e^{2\pi i r n / 8}$ where r ranges from 0 to 7.

By expressing the trigonometric functions in terms of complex exponentials using Euler's formula, we can relate the sequence's harmonic components to the characters of C_8 . Specifically, the terms $\cos\left(\frac{\pi n k}{4}\right)$, can be written as combinations of $e^{2\pi i k n / 8}$ and $e^{-2\pi i k n / 8}$.

This connection suggests that the sequence's terms can be viewed as evaluations of characters of representations of C_8 or its subgroups. The exact matching of frequencies and coefficients suggests that the sequence embodies the action of group representations.

3.3 Connection to Modular Forms

3.3.1 Modular Forms and Fourier Expansions

Modular forms are complex analytic functions on the upper half-plane that are invariant under the action of the modular group $SL_2(\mathbb{Z})$ up to a multiplier. They have Fourier expansions:

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n e^{2\pi i n z},$$

Where z is in the upper half-plane, and a_n are complex coefficients with deep arithmetic significance.

3.3.2 Potential Link with the Sequence

While this sequence is defined over integers, the harmonic components in its trigonometric formulation involve frequencies that are rational multiples of π , similar to the exponents in the Fourier expansions of modular forms.

By considering a function whose Fourier coefficients are related to the sequence's terms, we can explore the association of the sequence with a modular form of a certain level and weight. The precise harmonic components suggest that the sequence may correspond to the coefficients of a modular form or a theta function.

3.4 Connection to Number Theory

3.4.1 L-functions and Dirichlet Characters

L-functions are complex functions that generalize the Riemann zeta function and are constructed using Dirichlet characters or Fourier coefficients of modular forms. They play a crucial role in number theory, encoding significant arithmetic information.

3.4.2 Relation to the Sequence

If the sequence's terms are related to the Fourier coefficients of a modular form, they can potentially contribute to the construction of an L-function. The harmonic analysis of the sequence may reveal arithmetic properties encoded within the terms.

For instance, if we can express $a(n)$ in terms of Dirichlet characters or identify arithmetic patterns in the sequence, we can explore connections to Dirichlet L-functions or more general automorphic L-functions.

4. Family of Sequences and Their Properties

All member sequences in this family has its own period N and harmonic components, but all share the following properties:

- **Periodic Structure:** Each Sequence repeats after a fixed number of terms.
- **Harmonic Composition:** Each Sequence can be exactly represented as a finite sum of cosine functions with specific frequencies and amplitudes.
- **Symmetry and Oscillation:** The sequences exhibit symmetrical patterns and oscillate among a set of integer values.

- **Mathematical Connections:** They all have potential links to harmonic analysis, representation theory, and number theory, similar to the sequence discussed.

The study of interrelationships of this family of sequences opens up avenues for deeper exploration into their collective properties and the mathematical principles governing them.

5. Potential Applications and Implications

The characteristics shared by this family of sequences suggest implications and applications across multiple domains, of which we point to a few.

5.1 Mathematical Physics

- **Quantum Mechanics and Wave Functions:** The exact harmonic representations align with concepts in quantum mechanics, where wave functions are expressed as sums of harmonic components.
- **Symmetry Groups in Physics:** The connection to group representations may have implications in the study of symmetry groups in physics, aiding in the classification of particles and interactions.

5.2 Cryptography

- **Pseudo-Random Number Generation:** The sequences' complexity and predictability over a fixed period could be useful in designing pseudo-random number generators with specific properties.
- **Coding Theory:** The harmonic structure may contribute to the development of error-detecting and error-correcting codes, enhancing data transmission reliability.

5.3 Signal Processing

- **Discrete Signal Analysis:** The sequences can serve as test cases or building blocks in discrete signal processing, particularly in filtering and spectral analysis.
- **Compression Algorithms:** Understanding the harmonic components can lead to efficient data compression techniques by exploiting the sequences' inherent redundancies.

6. Conclusion

We have presented a periodic integer sequence and showed connections to harmonic analysis, representation theory, and potentially to modular forms and number theory. By demonstrating that the sequence can be exactly represented through its harmonic components, we have provided evidence of its mathematical significance.

As the simplest member of a broader family of sequences sharing similar properties, this sequence serves as a foundation for further research. Exploring this family may uncover deeper insights into the interplay between discrete sequences and continuous mathematical structures, with potential applications across various domains.

Acknowledgments

We thank the mathematical community for their contributions to harmonic analysis, representation theory, and number theory, which inspired and guided this contribution.

Authors contribution:

Abbas Shojaee initiated and conceived the concepts, which resulted in discovering the periodic sequences, developing the generating functions, and conducting mathematical analyses. **Yalda Arian** contributed to theoretical discussions, connecting the representation theory and harmonic analysis, and assisted in refining the presentation of the results. Both authors jointly wrote the manuscript.

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